

Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on
Advances in Civil and Environmental Engineering
Practices for Sustainable Development

ACEPS - 2019

Tsunami intrusion in rivers: A review and new perspectives on Sri Lankan rivers

Romitha Wickramasinghe¹, Norio Tanka²

¹Student, Graduate School of Science and Engineering, Saitama University, 255 Shimo-Okubo, Sakura-ku Saitama, 338-8570, Japan. Email: prabhathromitha@gmail.com (Author for correspondence)

²Professor, International Institute for Resilient Society, Graduate School of Science and Engineering, Saitama University, 255 Shimo-Okubo, Sakura-ku Saitama, 338-8570, Japan. Email: tanaka01@mail.saitama-u.ac.jp

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received

Revised

Accepted

Available online

Keywords:

Tsunami propagation

River mouth

Bed slope

Sand mining

River morphology

Sri Lanka

ABSTRACT

Tsunami intrusion in rivers can cause damages to near coast as well as upstream rivers. This paper reviews the role of different river parameters that dominate the phenomenon of tsunami propagation in rivers. River mouth morphology is the most influencing feature during a low magnitude tsunami, and bed slope acts major in an extreme event. Nevertheless, length and the impact of tsunami wave propagation in rivers depend on numerous features like tides, river discharge, meandering, river structures, flow branches and characteristics of embankments. During 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami in Sri Lanka, tsunami waves propagated significantly through a small river canal in Galle city causing local floods while the tsunami intruded in major rivers were dissipated due to existence of vast flood plains with trees around river mouths. This review also concentrates on human involvement to the evaluation of river morphology in Sri Lanka where unregulated sand mining has reduced the sediment supply to river mouth which can aggravate erosion during a tsunami event. Therefore, further investigations on small to mid-size rivers and quantitative analysis on the evolution of river morphology in Sri Lanka are vital for the management of potential tsunami related damage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tsunamis are a series of ocean waves that send surges of water caused by earthquakes, underwater landslides, volcanic eruptions, or asteroids. Generally, it is called a wave train, where its destructive force may be able to travel 10-15 meters per second with having wave height of 03-30 meters causing catastrophic damage to both the coast and in the hinterlands.

There have been reported cases where tsunami intrusion in the river leads to damages the areas far upstream from the shoreline, in addition to its capability of damaging coastal facilities and structures. Then the possibilities for the tsunami disaster always exist near the coastal and upstream areas both. Tsunami waves propagate to river may not only a threat of damages to the infrastructure but also cause

the environmental problems such as inundation and saline water intrusion to the rice field areas (H. Tanaka & Tinh 2012). Therefore, the study of tsunami impacts on river upstream becomes vital. Even though tsunami impacts on coastal areas have been subjected to countless studies, only a few studies have focused on tsunami impacts on rivers.

Hatori (1980) has reported some historical tsunamis originated in 1707 and 1854 in the Pacific Ocean of southwestern Japan, which caused inundations along the rivers. During the 1983 tsunami in Japan, Abe (1986) has recorded about development of a standing wave that propagated the tsunami wave up to 15km upstream of a river. Abe (1986) and Tolkova *et al* (2015) have reported that the peak of intruded tsunami wave height lies approximately midway between the river

mouth and the uppermost limit of tsunami inundation. Based on laboratory experiment and theoretical approach Tsuji *et al* (1991) found that the tsunami height in river might be amplified by a factor of 1.5 times the initial tsunami height in deep rivers or channels. This factor of increase can be used for the effective planning of river channel levees. According to N. Tanaka *et al* (2012), the 2011 Great East Japan Tsunami (GEJT) had hit some hinterlands from both river and coastal directions during the Great East Japan Earthquake while making the evacuation process complex.

Tsunami observations in rivers also include records of several tsunamis on tide gauges in the Columbia River. It was disclosed that tsunami penetrated the Columbia River, and was influenced by a combination of convergent bathymetry and bed friction. Moreover, its high-frequency components were controlled by diffusion and scattering in the river estuary (Yeh *et al.* 2012). Comparison of observed data of 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami (IOT), 2010 Chilean Earthquake Tsunami (CET) and 2011 GEJT unveil the importance of river mouth morphology in terms of tsunami wave propagation along a river (Adityawan *et al.* 2012; H. Tanaka & Tinh 2012; Roh *et al.* 2011). Moreover, Mori *et al* (2011) have observed longest runups in the 2011 GEJT and the 2010 CET. Fritz *et al* (2011) have identified wave propagated 15 km up in Maule river in Chile during 2010 CET. H. Tanaka *et al* (2014) was mentioned that during the 2011 GEJT, waves propagated in Kitakami river reached to 49 km from river mouth even after overtopping from a weir. As stated by Liu *et al* (2013), devastating tsunami inundation in the riverine plains of Kessen and Yahagi rivers have occurred where the propagated lengths are about four times the inundation distance in coastal area. A detailed study done in Sri Lanka after 2004 IOT reports that intruded tsunami waves to Sri Lankan rivers were mainly dissipated by vast flood plains around the river mouth (H. Tanaka *et al.* 2008).

Along with observational and experimental studies, numerical simulations also have provided confident results in the area of tsunami intrusion in rivers. Yasuda (2010) has conducted a 1D numerical model on tsunami propagation up in river channels while computational results agree well with the

observed data in 2003 Hokkaido tsunami in Japan. Viana-Baptista *et al* (2006) had conducted a numerical simulation for Tagus estuary, Lisbon, based on historical events of tsunami propagation in river that caused severe flooding in the upstream area. After the Columbia River affected by the 2011 GEJT, Tolkova (2013) simulated the event that populated with realistic tide and riverine flow. It also confirmed the occurrence of a tide-tsunami interaction by reproducing the observed modulation of tsunami by tide. As claimed by Tolkova *et al* (2015), observations of the 2011 GEJT and the 2010 CET in several rivers in Japan and the Columbia River in the USA described two tsunami effects in rivers. First, the river tide modulates the tsunami wave, and a strong near-field tsunami can cause significant prolonged water accumulation in lower river reaches. Using a simplified 1D nonlinear shallow-water model, the numerical experiments highlight the indispensable role of tsunami's interaction with tide and riverine flow (Tolkova *et al.* 2015).

Moreover, to evaluate the wave heights of incident and reflected tsunami bores in Katakami River during 2011 GEJT, Tolkova & H. Tanaka (2016) have exercised the shock conditions with actual tsunami measurements in the river. These distinguishing features make this study relevant to enhance knowledge further on the phenomena of tsunami intrusion in rivers. This review focuses on parameters that dominate the tsunami intrusion in rivers and understand the research gaps in this sector in Sri Lanka.

2. EFFECT OF RIVER PARAMETERS

2.1. River Mouth Morphology

The tsunami wave propagating in rivers is related to various river parameters. In wave propagation process, river mouth morphology is one of the dominant factors because it is the entrance location of the wave (Adityawan *et al.* 2012; H. Tanaka & Tinh 2012; Roh *et al.* 2011).

Analyzing the data of the 2010 CET, Roh *et al* (2011) have mentioned the influence of the river characteristic on tsunami propagation including a numerical model. In the study, they have classified river mouth into two types (Figure 1) where Type 1 river mouth is located

1

2
3

4 Figure 1: Examples for classification of river mouth types in Sri Lanka (Source: Google Maps). Modified
5 from H. Tanaka & Tinh (2012).

6
7 inside of port or bay (non-constriction form),
8 and Type 2 is that river mouth is composed by
9 sand bar or sandy coast at river entrance
10 (constriction form). The reasonable and
11 consistent results of collected data and
12 numerical analysis show that the defined Type
13 1 has a high vulnerability, where the most
14 influential type of river mouth when the
15 tsunami wave approaches the river area.
16 Focusing on the impacts of the 2010 CET and
17 the 2011 GEJT with respect to 25 rivers in
18 Tohoku region of Japan, H. Tanaka & Tinh
19 (2012) also has found Type 1 river mouths are
20 vulnerable in terms of wave height and
21 upstream propagation. Moreover, tsunami
22 wave can be affected up to about 50km
23 upstream of a large river and the measured
24 tsunami travel time inside the river is almost
25 similar to tsunami travel time calculated by
26 using the long-wave theory (H. Tanaka & Tinh
27 2012).

28
29 Selecting rivers in Sendai coast-Japan and Aceh
30 coast-Indonesia, Adityawan *et al* (2012) further
31 elucidate the tsunami intrusion in rivers
32 relating to three tsunamis caused by the 2004
33 IOT, the 2010 CET, and the 2011 GEJT. It
34 delineates that river mouth morphological
35 features play an essential role in the intrusion
36 of low magnitude tsunami; nevertheless, the
37 effect of these features is less significant in the
38 case of an extreme tsunami.

39
40 Naturally formed river mouths with buffer
41 have a greater capability on reducing tsunami

42 wave energy compared to river mouths with
43 no buffer (H. Tanaka *et al.* 2014). It was
44 recorded that there was an initial reduction in
45 propagated tsunami wave height in Agano
46 River due to existence of sandbars at the river
47 mouth, which was exposed to the 1983
48 tsunami in Japan (Abe 1986). Moreover, N.
49 Tanaka *et al* (2012) also reports about the
50 existence of sand-dune in the Mikawa River
51 where most of the tsunami was stopped in the
52 2011 GEJT.

53
54 Based on Sri Lankan catastrophe in 2004, H.
55 Tanaka *et al* (2008) states that the distance of
56 tsunami propagation in Sri Lankan rivers is
57 dependent more on the scale of flood plains on
58 both sides of the river, rather than on the size
59 of the river mouth bar.

60 2.2. Bed Slope

61 River bed slope plays a major role in the wave
62 propagation in extreme tsunami events. Since
63 tsunami wave can propagate easily into river
64 upstream area through steady and mild type
65 river bed without losing large amount of wave
66 energy, Adityawan *et al* (2012) reports that
67 tsunami intrusion in river due to massive
68 tsunamis like the 2004 IOT and the 2011 GEJT
69 is correlated to the bed slope with no
70 significant effect from the river class or type of
71 the river mouth. During the 2004 IOT, waves
72 surged up along the small river canal with
73 very mild bed slopes (Kapu Ela) in Galle city
74 of Sri Lanka for approximately 2km upstream
75 and caused localized flooding (H. Tanaka *et al.*
76 2008).

77

1 The observational and numerical data of
2 Tolkova *et al* (2015) point to a correlation
3 between the tsunami attenuation rate and the
4 river bed slope in the tsunami path as well as a
5 similar correlation between the tsunami
6 intrusion distance and the river bed slope. H.
7 Tanaka *et al* (2014) states that damping
8 coefficient is closely related to the riverbed
9 slope and river meandering may have
10 different effect on this parameter.

12 2.3. Other Parameters

13 Apart from characteristics of river mouth and
14 bed, there are other features that influence
15 tsunami propagation through rivers. As per
16 the previous studies, it is assumed that the
17 outer bank side of a river meander is more
18 vulnerable to overtopping during wave
19 propagation in a river (Shi *et al.* 1998; Yuhi *et*
20 *al.* 2000). In the studies of Abe (1986) and N.
21 Tanaka *et al* (2012) have found that the river
22 embankments were overtopped at a
23 meandering river section during tsunami
24 wave propagation along the rivers.
25 Furthermore, Abe (1986) concluded that
26 various factors such as flow branching and
27 artificial water intakes may complicate the
28 propagation profiles during a tsunami event.
29 According to Roh *et al* (2011), tsunami waves
30 are transmitted even in the low tidal level
31 which will govern by river scale, river
32 discharge and the bottom condition. Tolkova
33 *et al* (2015) report that tsunami penetration in
34 rivers is largely determined by the interaction
35 among the flow components such as tsunami
36 wave strength, tide, and river discharge.
37 According to H. Tanaka *et al* (2008) strength of
38 the abutment also plays an important role to
39 withstand large return flow in rivers.

40
41 Based on available tsunami records in the
42 Columbia River, USA Tolkova (2013)
43 suggested that non-linear interaction between
44 tsunami and river tide causes attenuation of
45 tsunami signal during the receding tide in the
46 river estuary, and facilitates tsunami
47 propagation and confirmed this hypothesis in
48 numerical simulations of tsunami intrusion
49 into the Columbia River. Numerical
50 simulation of Tolkova *et al* (2015) has disclosed
51 that high tide greatly facilitates the tsunami
52 intrusion, whereas a receding tide efficiently
53 dissipates the tsunami energy. Generated
54 backwater effect during a tsunami
55 propagation in a river can obstruct the river

56 flow and lead to overtopping from
57 embankments. Tolkova *et al* (2015) have
58 hypothesized and briefly illustrated this
59 condition with numerical experiments.
60 Having river structures like weirs can mitigate
61 the tsunami propagation in a river, and it was
62 observed during the Kitakami River and the
63 Abukuma River in the 2011 GEJT (H. Tanaka
64 *et al.* 2014). However, H. Tanaka *et al* (2014)
65 stated that reflected tsunami wave due to
66 structure can increase the inundation in
67 downstream area.

68
69 In the 2011 GEJT, N. Tanaka *et al* (2012)
70 discovered that tsunami can hit from both
71 directions from coast and river to hinterlands.
72 Situations like this have made the flow
73 conditions and evacuation process of people
74 complex during the propagation. According to
75 H. Tanaka *et al* (2008), similar kind of
76 inundation type was observed in the Galle city
77 during 2004 IOT (Figure 2). This elucidates the
78 necessity of identifying vulnerable
79 embankment locations and inundation types
80 during an event to upgrade hazard maps as
81 well as plan new cities.

83 3. TSUNAMI INTRUSION IN SRI 84 LANKAN RIVERS

85 The IOT triggered on 26th December 2004
86 caused a massive loss of life and damage to
87 property in the coastal belts of several Indian
88 Ocean countries including Sri Lanka,
89 Indonesia, and Thailand. Sri Lanka has been
90 extremely hard-hit from this IOT in terms of
91 loss of life, infrastructure, and economic assets
92 where the 2004 IOT is widely acknowledged as
93 the largest and most devastating natural
94 catastrophe in the history of the country.

95
96 According to Wijetunge (2004), it left behind
97 widespread destruction and killed nearly
98 40,000 people with 15,000 injured, destroyed
99 over 89,000 homes entirely or partially,
100 damaged natural ecosystems, and coastal
101 infrastructure. The incurred overall damage is
102 estimated to be around \$1 billion, which is
103 almost 4.5 percent of country's GDP (ADB
104 2005).

105
106 Studies on tsunami intrusion to rivers in Sri
107 Lanka is rare. However, a detailed study was
108 conducted by H. Tanaka *et al* (2008) targeting
109 Kalu Ganga, Gin Ganga, Galle city, Nilwala
110 Ganga, Mahaweli River, and Yan Oya after the

1 Table 1: Characteristic of rivers. Modified from H. Tanaka *et al* (2008).

Name of River	Size of Sand Bar	Status of River Banks	Distance of Propagation (Approx.)	Degree of Tsunami Energy Dissipation
Kalu	Large	Narrow flood plain	20km	Small
Gin	Small	Vast flood plain	5-6km	Large
Nilwala	Large	Vast flood plain with tress	8km	Medium
Yan	Medium	Dense tress	3-4km	Large
Mahaweli	Medium	Vast flood plain with tress	Unknown	Large

2

3 2004 IOT and observed field data are shown in
4 Table 1.

5
6 Analyzing the data of Gin Ganga, Yan Oya and
7 Mahaweli River, H. Tanaka *et al* (2008) has
8 revealed that the distance of tsunami
9 propagation is dependent more on the scale of
10 flood plains on both sides of the river, rather
11 than on the size of the river mouth bar. In the
12 same event, they have discovered that the
13 tsunami intrusion along small river canals
14 named Kapu Ela and Moragoda river inside in
15 Galle city extending the impact of tsunami
16 approximately 2km and 1km respectively in
17 upstream area. It had caused flooding from
18 both sea and river, where this inundation type
19 (Figure 2) was similar to which was observed
20 by N. Tanaka *et al* (2012) during the 2011 GEJT
21 in Abukumagawa and Kitakamigawa Rivers
22 in Japan.

23

24
25

26 Figure 2: Inundation type of Galle city during
27 the 2004 IOT (Source: Google Maps). Modified
28 from N. Tanaka *et al* (2012).

29
30 Among the infrastructure damages, bridge
31 damages were vital in the west and south
32 coasts of Sri Lanka, where railway line and
33 main road (A2) cross several rivers and
34 streams. Here, H. Tanaka *et al* (2008) had

35 underlined the importance of detail analysis of
36 tsunami effect on bridges with regard to future
37 bridge designing while investigating and
38 categorizing 34 bridges, culverts and their
39 surrounding structures based on the damage.
40 Since most of the Sri Lankan railway bridges
41 are through bridges, and most of the road
42 bridges are deck bridges, the clearance height
43 between the girder and the water surface of
44 railway bridges is higher than that of the road
45 bridges. Therefore, the damage sustained by
46 railway bridges is less compared to road
47 bridges (H. Tanaka *et al* 2008). Additionally, in
48 the study of Rossetto *et al.* (2007), it has
49 identified three common bridge types based
50 on the span in the surveyed areas which were
51 affected by 2004 IOT. It has found that between
52 Kaluthara and Matara, five road bridges and
53 four railway bridges were severely damaged
54 where most of the bridges consisted of damage
55 to parapets or abutments. According to
56 Rossetto *et al.* (2007), the primary mode of
57 failure of the road bridges was the collapse of
58 the concrete deck slab because of consequent
59 failure of the masonry retaining wall
60 abutments due to scouring. Even though the
61 abutments of these bridges consisted of rock
62 barrier on sea side, it lacked similar protection
63 on upstream side which led to erosion, caused
64 by backflow of propagated tsunami wave
65 along the river.

66

67 Introducing a comparison concept of
68 discharge and flow velocity of a flood induced
69 by torrential rain and tsunami waves in small
70 and large rivers, H. Tanaka *et al* (2008)
71 reported that, due to tsunami waves, the
72 damage sustained by a bridge of a large river
73 is relatively small compared to the damage
74 sustained by a bridge of small rivers.
75 Therefore, the lessons learned from the
76 damage to the river bridges in Sri Lankan

1 southwest can be used for planning and
2 implementing necessary prior measures in
3 bridge design in other countries. H. Tanaka *et*
4 *al* (2008) indicates that the damage becomes
5 more severe in terms of bridge collapse as the
6 ratio of “tsunami wave height/bridge
7 clearance height” exceeds 2.0. This can be used
8 to estimate the severity of bridge damages in
9 future tsunami events.

10

11 In addition, Richmond *et al* (2006) claims that
12 the removal of sand-dunes and extensive
13 illegal dredging in rivers appear to have
14 increased the inundation in the first place of
15 tsunami in Sri Lanka. According to
16 Samaranayake (2005), sand mining in Sri
17 Lankan rivers not only resulted in a lower river
18 bed and increased bank erosion, but also
19 drastically reduced the sediment supply to the
20 coast which increases the vulnerability of
21 tsunami intrusion through river mouths.

22

23 4. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

24 It was reported that damages due to tsunami
25 intrusion in rivers can be more devastating
26 due to its high potential to propagate in rivers
27 compared to land. This phenomenon is mainly
28 dominated by river morphology. In Sri Lanka,
29 tsunami intrusion in rivers has obtained less
30 attention, where integrated studies are
31 required in future particularly considering the
32 small and mid-sized rivers. Secondly, human
33 impacts on river morphology also have greater
34 influence on the evolution of river mouths and
35 river bed. Indiscriminate and extensive sand
36 mining in rivers, beaches, and dunes have
37 triggered to loss of natural sand bars in river
38 mouths. This loss increases the vulnerability of
39 tsunami intrusion. Further it also reduces the
40 amount of sand available to replenish what
41 was lost during the tsunami events. Hence
42 quantitative analysis should be attained to
43 investigate the evolution of river mouth
44 morphology.

45 5. REFERENCES

46 Abe, K., 1986, ‘Tsunami propagation in rivers
47 of the Japanese Islands’, *Continental Shelf*
48 *Research* 5(6), 665–677.
49 Adityawan, M.B., Roh, M., Tanaka, H., Farid,
50 M., 2012, ‘The Effect of River Mouth
51 Morphological Features on Tsunami
52 Intrusion’, *Proceedings of the 8th International*

53 *Conference on Disaster Management*, pp. 75–83.

54 Asian Development Bank, 2005, ‘Sri Lanka
55 2005 Post-Tsunami Recovery Program -
56 Preliminary Damage and Needs Assessment’,
57 Colombo, Sri Lanka: Asian Development
58 Bank, Japan Bank for International
59 Cooperation and, World Bank.

60 Fritz, H.M., Petroff, C.M., Catalán, P.A.,
61 Cienfuegos, R., Winckler, P., Kalligeris, N.,
62 Weiss, R., Barrientos, S.E., Meneses, G.,
63 Valderas-Bermejo, C., Ebeling, C.,
64 Papadopoulos, A., Contreras, M., Almar, R.,
65 Dominguez, J.C., Synolakis, C.E., 2011, ‘Field
66 Survey of the 27 February 2010 Chile
67 Tsunami’, *Pure Appl. Geophys* 168, 1989–2010.

68 Hatori, T., 1980, ‘Field Investigation of the
69 Nankaido Tsunamis in 1707 and 1854 along
70 the Osaka and Wakayama Coasts, West Kii
71 Peninsula’. *Bull. of the Earthq. Res. Inst.*,
72 University of Tokyo, 55, pp. 505–535.

73 Liu, H., Shimozone, T., Takagawa, T.,
74 Okayasu, A., Fritz, H.M., Sato, S., Tajima, Y.,
75 2013, ‘The 11 March 2011 Tohoku Tsunami
76 Survey in Rikuzentakata and Comparison
77 with Historical Events’, *Pure Appl. Geophys*
78 170, 1033–1046.

79 Mori, N., Takahashi, T., Yasuda, T.,
80 Yanagisawa, H., 2011, ‘Survey of 2011 Tohoku
81 earthquake tsunami inundation and run-up’,
82 *Geophysical Research Letters* 38, 6–11.

83 Richmond, B.M., Jaffe, B.E., Gelfenbaum, G.,
84 Morton, R.A., 2006, ‘Geologic impacts of the
85 2004 Indian ocean tsunami on Indonesia, Sri
86 Lanka, and the Maldives’, *Z. Geomorphol.* 146,
87 235–251.

88 Roh, M., Nguyen, X.T., Tanaka, H., 2011,
89 ‘Effect of river mouth morphology on tsunami
90 propagation ascending rivers’, *J. Japan Soc.*
91 *Civ. Eng. Ser. A2 (Applied Mech.)* 67(2), 607-
92 I_614.

93 Rossetto, T., Peiris, N., Pomonis, A.,
94 Wilkinson, S.M., Del Re, D., Koo, R., Gallocher,
95 S., 2007, ‘The Indian Ocean tsunami of
96 December 26, 2004: Observations in Sri Lanka
97 and Thailand’, *Nat. Hazards* 42, 105–124.

98 Samaranayake, R. A. D. B., 2006, ‘Pre-and
99 post-tsunami coastal planning and land-use
100 policies and issues in Sri Lanka’, *In proceedings*
101 *of the workshop on coastal area planning and*
102 *management in Asian tsunami-affected countries,*
103 Bangkok, Thailand, Food and Agriculture

- 1 Organization of the United Nations, pp. 27–29.
- 2 Shi, A., Teng, M.H., Wu, T.Y., 1998,
3 `Propagation of solitary waves through
4 significantly curved shallow water channels`.
5 *J. Fluid Mech.* 362, 157–176.
- 6 Tanaka, H., Ishono, K., Nawarathna, B.,
7 Nakagawa, H., Yasuda, H., Watanabe, Y.,
8 Hasegawa, K., 2008, `Field Investigation of
9 Disasters in Sri Lankan Rivers Caused By the
10 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami`, *J. Hydrosoci.*
11 *Hydraul. Eng.* 26(1), 91–112.
- 12 Tanaka, H., Kayane, K., Adityawan, M.B., Roh,
13 M., Farid, M., 2014, `Study on the relation of
14 river morphology and tsunami propagation in
15 rivers`, *Ocean Dyn.* 64, 1319–1322.
- 16 Tanaka, H., Tinh, N.X., 2012, `The 2010
17 Chilean and the 2011 Tohoku Tsunami Waves
18 Impact to Rivers in the Tohoku Region, Japan`.
19 *In proceedings of 33rd International Conference on
20 Coastal Engineering.*
- 21 Tanaka, N., Yagisawa, J., Yasuda, S., 2012,
22 `Characteristics of damage due to tsunami
23 propagation in river channels and overflow of
24 their embankments in Great East Japan
25 Earthquake`. *Int. J. River Basin Manag.* 10(3),
26 269–279.
- 27 Tolkova, E., 2013, `Tide-Tsunami Interaction
28 in Columbia River, as Implied by Historical
29 Data and Numerical Simulations`, *Pure Appl.*
30 *Geophys.* 170, 1115–1126.
- 31 Tolkova, E., Tanaka, H., Roh, M., 2015,
32 `Tsunami Observations in Rivers from a
33 Perspective of Tsunami Interaction with Tide
34 and Riverine Flow`, *Pure Appl. Geophys.* 172,
35 953–968.
- 36 Tolkova, E., Tanaka, H., 2016, `Tsunami Bores
37 in Kitakami River`, *Pure Appl. Geophys.* 173(12),
38 4039–4054.
- 39 Tsuji, Y., Yanuma, T., Murata, I., Fujiwara, C.,
40 1991, `Tsunami ascending in rivers as an
41 undular bore`, *Nat. Hazards* 4, 257–266.
- 42 Viana-Baptista, M.A., Soares, P.M., Miranda,
43 J.M., Luis, J.F., 2006, `Tsunami Propagation
44 Along Tagus Estuary (Lisbon, Portugal)
45 Preliminary Results`, *Sci. Tsunami Hazards*
46 24(5), 329–338.
- 47 Wijetunge, J.J., 2004, `Tsunami On 26
48 December 2004: Spatial Distribution Of
49 Tsunami Height And The Extent Of
50 Inundation In Sri Lanka`, *Sci. Tsunami Hazards*
51 24(3), 225–239.
- 52 Yasuda, H., 2010, `One-dimensional study on
53 propagation of tsunami wave in river
54 channels`, *J. Hydraul. Eng.* 136(2), 93–105.
- 55 Yeh, H., Tolkova, E., Jay, D., Talke, S., Fritz, H.,
56 2012, `Tsunami hydrodynamics in the
57 Columbia River`, *J. Disaster Res.* 7(5), 604–608.
- 58 Yuhi, M., Ishida, H., Mase, H., 2000,
59 `Numerical study of solitary wave
60 propagation in curved channels`, *Coast. Eng.*
61 *2000 - Proc. 27th Int. Conf. Coast. Eng.* Sydney,
62 Australia, July 16–21, 2000, pp. 519–532.
- 63